

ORGANIZATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS ON THE LEARNERS' ACHIEVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the level of organizational leadership and communication skills on the learners' achievement, the academic performance of the learners during the School Year 2022-2023, the significant relationship between the variables, and the challenges encountered by learners and teachers. Employing a quantitative method using descriptive-correlational research design with the adopted instrument from National Education Association Teacher Leadership Institute (2022), data was gathered from 243 learners and 71 teachers in public secondary schools in San Vicente, Camarines Norte. To analyze the data, weighted mean and Pearson r Correlation Coefficient were used. Findings revealed that teachers and school heads exhibit strong leadership and communication skills. It also revealed improved academic performance of the learners during the school year 2022-2023. Moreover, the challenge encountered the need for additional training or resources. Furthermore, there is no significant relationship between the leadership skills and learners' academic performance. Findings revealed no significant relationship between the communication skills and learners' academic performance. With these results, this study recommended a three-day training workshop in respond to the challenges encountered by the teachers for the need of training workshop to enhance their skills. It is hereby recommended that teacher training programs may incorporate leadership skills development to prepare educators for leadership roles and equip them with the necessary skills to address complex challenges effectively.

Keywords: *Leadership Skills, Communication Skills, Learners' Achievement*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership and communication skills are two important factors in an organizational performance. Leadership skills are a diverse set of characteristics and abilities that enable an individual to guide, inspire, and effectively influence a group or organization (Abbas et al. 2020). On the other hand, communication skills are the foundation of effective human interaction. They cover a wide range of skills, from verbal and nonverbal communication to active listening and emotional intelligence. Effective communicators express their ideas in a clear and concise manner, ensuring that their message is easily understood (Yasar, 2020). Conversely, the leadership and communication are two skills which are crucial in the educational perspectives which contribute to improving the quality of education and especially the learners' achievement.

In public secondary schools in San Vicente, numerous challenges arise that require strong organizational leadership, particularly in the realm of communication skills. One prevalent problem is the lack of clear communication channels. Inefficient communication within the school organization results in confusion, misunderstandings, and delays in disseminating crucial information to staff, students, and parents. This not only impacts day-to-day operations but also hinders the school organization's responsiveness to emerging challenges and opportunities. All these challenges are present in Fabrica High School and Froilan D. Lopez High School.

The nature of public education involves large student populations, limited resources, and demanding workloads for educators. In these environments, the role of organizational leadership in fostering a positive and engaging workplace through effective communication becomes paramount. The teachers feel disconnected from the broader goals and vision of the school, which results in widespread dissatisfaction and reduced commitment to the institution's mission. Thus, resistance to change is also a problem and conflicts among teachers is also worsened by poor communication practices.

The primary goal of this study is to investigate the relationship between effective leadership in educational settings and academic success, the role of communication skills in the teaching and learning process, and provide actionable insights for educators to refine their instructional approaches. Also, this will determine how leadership and communication skills contribute to the development of a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Another goal is to determine how leadership and communication skills affect student motivation and self-efficacy.

Research Questions

This study determined the organizational leadership and communication skills on the learners' achievement. Specifically, this sought answers to the following:

1. What is the level of leadership skills of respondents in terms of leading innovation, critical thinking, and problem-solving?

2. What is the level of communication skills of the respondents in terms of listening, speaking, and writing?
3. What is the academic performance of the learners during the School Year 2022-2023?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the leadership skills and learners' academic performance?
5. Is there significant relationship between the communication skills and learners' academic performance?
6. What are the challenges encountered by learners and teachers in the organizational leadership and communication skills of the school heads and teachers?
7. What intervention may be proposed to enhance the leadership and communication skills of school heads and teachers?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quantitative method using a descriptive-correlational research design. The researcher employed a descriptive study to the level of organizational leadership and communication skills on the learners' achievement and the challenges encountered by the respondents. To find out if a variable has a relationship with another variable, correlational research was also conducted.

This study adapted the survey questionnaire from the National Education Association Teacher Leadership Institute (2022). Part 1 encompassed the leadership skills of respondents in terms of leading innovation, critical thinking and problem-solving. Part 2 contained 5 indicators about the leadership skills of teachers and school heads. Part 3 included the communication skills of the respondents in terms of listening, speaking and writing. Part 4 was the academic performance of the learners in school year 2022-2023. Part 4 involved the challenges encountered by teachers and learners in the organizational leadership and communication skills of the school heads and teachers.

This study employed stratified random sampling of 243 learners while total enumeration of 71 teachers in secondary schools in San Vicente, Camarines Norte participated in this study. For data tabulation and analysis in this study, Microsoft Excel, online Pearson r Correlation Coefficient calculator and IBM SPSS Statistics Version 21 were used. To determine the level of organizational leadership and communication skills on the learners' achievement, and the challenges encountered by the respondents, the researcher utilized weighted mean as a measure of central tendency. To analyze the significant relationships between variables, the researcher used online Pearson r Correlation Coefficient calculator.

RESULTS

Level of Leadership Skills of Teachers and School Heads. Table 1 presents the leadership skills of teachers and school heads along leading innovation, as indicated by various factors such as promoting a culture of creativity, encouraging continuous learning, facilitating collaboration, providing resources and support, and celebrating innovation. The overall level of leadership skills in leading innovation, with a score of 3.44

interpreted as “Strongly Agree” among teacher respondents while 3.06 interpreted as “Agree” among school head respondents.

Table 1
Leadership Skills of Teachers and School Heads along Leading Innovation

Indicator	Teacher		School Head	
	WM	Verbal Interpretation	WM	Verbal Interpretation
Promotes a culture of creativity and risk-taking	3.13	Agree	3.23	Agree
Encourages continuous learning and development	3.94	Strongly Agree	3.07	Agree
Facilitates cross-functional collaboration	3.93	Strongly Agree	3.17	Agree
Provides resources and support	3.15	Agree	2.90	Agree
Celebrates and recognizes innovation	3.07	Agree	2.94	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.44	Strongly Agree	3.06	Agree
Rating Scale:	3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree		2.51 – 3.25 – Agree	
	1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree		1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree	

Critical Thinking. Table 2 presents the level of critical thinking skills among teachers and school heads, focusing on indicators such as encouraging questioning and reflection, promoting open communication, challenging assumptions, facilitating problem-solving discussions, and modeling critical thinking behaviors. The overall level of critical thinking skills, with a score of 3.14 interpreted as “Agree” among teacher respondents while 2.94 score for school heads.

Table 2
Leadership Skills of Teachers and School Heads along Critical Thinking

Indicator	Teacher		School Heads	
	WM	Verbal Interpretation	WM	Verbal Interpretation
Encourages questioning and reflection	3.98	Strongly Agree	3.01	Agree
Promotes open communication	3.11	Agree	3.11	Agree
Challenges assumptions	3.07	Agree	2.94	Agree
Facilitates problem-solving discussions	2.33	Disagree	2.77	Agree
Models critical thinking behaviors	3.18	Agree	2.85	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.14	Agree	2.94	Agree
Rating Scale:	3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree		2.51 – 3.25 – Agree	
	1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree		1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree	

Problem-solving. Table 3 presents the level of problem-solving skills among teachers and school heads, focusing on indicators such as strong analytical skills, agility

in decision-making, fostering collaborative environments, exploring unconventional solutions, and promoting proactive problem-solving cultures. The overall level of problem-solving skills, with a score of 3.48 interpreted as “Strongly Agree” among teacher respondents while a score of 2.89 (Agree) for school heads.

Table 3
Leadership Skills of Teachers and School Heads along Problem-Solving

Indicator	Teachers		School Heads	
	WM	Verbal Interpretation	WM	Verbal Interpretation
Demonstrates strong analytical skills, breaking down complex problems into manageable components	3.94	Strongly Agree	2.79	Agree
Exhibits agility in decision-making	3.20	Agree	3.11	Agree
Fosters a collaborative problem-solving environment	3.10	Agree	2.80	Agree
Explores unconventional solutions encouraging creativity and adaptability	3.18	Agree	2.73	Agree
Fosters a culture where problem-solving is not just reactive but proactive	3.98	Strongly Agree	3.06	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.48	Strongly Agree	2.89	Agree
Rating Scale:	3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree	2.51 – 3.25 – Agree		
	1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree	1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree		

Level of Communication Skills of Teachers and School Heads. Table 4 illustrates the communication skills of teachers and school heads along listening. The overall level of communication skills, with a score of 3.17 interpreted as “Agree” among teacher respondents and school heads with the score of 2.99.

Table 4
Communication Skills of Teachers and School Heads along Listening

Indicator	Teachers		School Heads	
	WM	Verbal Interpretation	WM	Verbal Interpretation
Demonstrates genuine interest for others	3.13	Agree	2.89	Agree
Exhibits empathy in their listening skills	3.22	Agree	3.27	Strongly Agree
Clarifies and summarize information to ensure accurate information	3.20	Agree	2.94	Agree
Attuned to non-verbal cues and recognizes meanings conveyed	3.13	Agree	2.96	Agree
Provides constructive and respectful feedback	3.17	Agree	2.90	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.17	Agree	2.99	Agree
Rating Scale:	3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree	2.51 – 3.25 – Agree		
	1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree	1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree		

Speaking Skills. Table 5 provides insights into the level of speaking skills among teachers and school heads. The overall level of speaking skills, with a score of 3.02 and 3.10 interpreted as “Agree” among respondents. The results suggest a positive perception of teachers' speaking skills, with agreement across most indicators.

Table 5
Communication Skills of Teachers and School Heads along Speaking

Indicator	Teachers		School Heads	
	WM	Verbal Interpretation	WM	Verbal Interpretation
Express themselves clearly and concisely	3.22	Agree	3.00	Agree
Adapts communication styles to suit audience	2.43	Disagree	3.23	Agree
Exhibit confidence and poise in speaking	3.21	Agree	3.17	Agree
Effectively uses verbal and non-verbal elements to enhance their message	3.08	Agree	3.17	Agree
Captures attention and facilitates better retention of information	3.17	Agree	2.94	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.02	Agree	3.10	Agree
Rating Scale:	3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree		2.51 – 3.25 – Agree	
	1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree		1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree	

Writing Skills. Table 6 presents the level of writing skills among teachers and school heads. The overall weighted mean reflects the overall level of writing skills, with a score of 3.15 and 3.05 interpreted as “Agree’ among respondents.

Table 6
Communication Skills of Teachers and School Heads along Writing

Indicator	Teachers		School Heads	
	WM	Verbal Interpretation	WM	Verbal Interpretation
Conveys ideas with clarity and coherence	3.16	Agree	2.99	Agree
Communicate effectively by being concise and precise in the use of language	3.17	Agree	3.01	Agree
Tailors their writing to meet the needs and expectations of the intended readers	3.16	Agree	3.11	Agree
Ensures that writing is grammatically correct and uses proper language	3.17	Agree	3.07	Agree
Writings are clear on the purpose	3.12	Agree	3.06	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.15	Agree	3.05	Agree
Rating Scale:	3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree		2.51 – 3.25 – Agree	
	1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree		1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree	

Academic Performance of the Learners. Table 7 displays the academic performance of learners in the School Year 2022-2023. The table presents the average grades achieved by students in Grades 9, 10, and 12, as well as the overall average across all grade levels. The table indicates that Grade 12 students achieved the highest average grade of 85.83, followed by Grade 10 students with an average of 85.20, and Grade 9 students with an average of 84.80. The overall average grade across all grade levels is 85.28. This suggests a generally consistent level of academic performance across the different grade levels during the specified school year.

Table 7
Academic Performance of the Learners in School Year 2022-2023

Grade Level	Average
9	84.80
10	85.20
12	85.83
Average	85.28

Relationship between the Leadership Skills of Teachers and Learners' Academic Performance. The test for significant relationship that may exist between the leadership skills in terms of leading and innovation, critical thinking and problem solving and the learners' academic performance was tested using the Pearsons Product Moment Correlation (*r*) at 0.05 level. It can be observed on Table 8 that the leadership skills among teachers as perceived by the students in terms of leading innovation, critical thinking and problem solving have no significant relationships to the learners' academic performance. The *p*-values are greater than 0.05 (*p*-values>0.05), meaning the correlation is not statistically significant. These findings suggest that while leadership skills maybe valued in various contexts and have their own significance, they do not directly impact the academic performance of the examined population.

Table 8
Test for Significant Relationship between the Leadership Skills and Learners' Academic Performance

Parameter	Leadership Skills					
	Leading Innovation		Critical Thinking		Problem-Solving	
	<i>R</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Learners' Academic Performance	.067	.297	.036	.577	.116	.072

Relationship between the Communication Skills and Learners' Academic Performance. The significant relationship that may exist between the communication skills in terms of listening, speaking and writing and the academic performance of the students were also tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (*r*). Table 9 reveals that the communication skills along listening, speaking and writing and the learners' academic performance failed to obtain significant relationship. The corresponding *p*-

values of *r* are all greater than 0.05 level. This means that the obtained *p*-values are not statistically significant. It suggests that the communication skills of the teachers as perceived by the students has nothing to do with the learners' academic performance. It is possible that the influence of communication skills of the teachers on academic performance of the students varies among individuals. Likewise, the results also indicate that there might be other skills aside from communication skills that might be relevant and crucial in determining the success in academics of the learners.

Table 9
Test for Significant Relationship between the Communication Skills and Learners' Academic Performance

Parameter	Communication Skills					
	Listening		Speaking		Writing	
	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Learners' Academic Performance	.007	.918	.039	.545	.062	.338

Challenges Encountered by Teachers and Learners in the Organizational Leadership and Communication Skills of the Teachers and School Heads. Table 10 presents the challenges encountered by teachers and learners in the organizational leadership and communication skills of school heads and teachers. The table shows a total weighted mean of 2.70 which means ang agreeable challenge as encountered by teachers and learners as a whole.

Table 10
Challenges Encountered by Teachers and Learners

Indicator	WM	Verbal Interpretation
1. Documented cases of instructions not being clearly conveyed, resulting in confusion among teachers and learners	2.57	Agree
2. Survey results or feedback sessions where teachers highlight the need for more training, workshops, or resources to enhance their skills	2.95	Agree
3. Reports of policies being applied unevenly or instances where teachers and learners experience different outcomes for similar situations	2.60	Agree
4. Feedback or survey responses indicating a desire for more collaborative decision-making forums or mechanisms	2.52	Agree
5. Reports of learners expressing concerns about the learning environment, teaching methodologies, or interpersonal dynamics within the school	2.88	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.70	Agree
Rating Scale: 3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree	2.51 – 3.25 – Agree	
1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree	1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree	

Intervention Proposed to Enhance the Leadership and Communication Skills of School Heads and Teachers. The study proposed a three-day training workshop in

respond to the challenges encountered by the teachers for the need of training workshop to enhance their skills.

DISCUSSION

Findings revealed the high level of agreement regarding the encouragement of continuous learning and development (3.94) which indicates that teachers play a pivotal role in fostering an environment that nurtures creativity, learning, and collaboration, thereby promoting innovation within the educational setting. The high scores in encouraging continuous learning and facilitating cross-functional collaboration reflect the commitment of teachers to fostering a dynamic and innovative learning environment. The lowest score which got 3.07 is the indicator “Celebrating and recognizing innovation”. This indicates that institutional culture is resistant to change, favoring traditional methods over innovative ones. The findings are in contrary from the study of Cimene et al. (2022) which found high evidence in the importance of continuous learning and development among teachers.

Findings revealed a generally positive perception of leadership skills among school heads in leading innovation. School heads are perceived to promote a culture of creativity and risk-taking (3.23). This means that they inspire others to think innovatively and embrace new ideas by communicating a compelling vision of what can be achieved through creativity and taking calculated risks. This also means that they model innovative behaviors and attitudes, inspiring others to embrace experimentation and push the boundaries of conventional thinking.

Additionally, leaders face constraints in budget allocation, limiting the availability of resources for innovation initiatives. As the findings revealed, the study by Zabala (2021) agreed which found that transformational leadership behaviors, such as promoting a shared vision and empowering others, are positively associated with organizational innovation.

The results revealed a generally positive perception of teachers' critical thinking skills, with a strong agreement in encouraging questioning and reflection (3.98). The findings suggested that teachers are adept at fostering environments that promote inquiry, reflection, and critical analysis. The high scores in encouraging questioning and reflection and modeling critical thinking behaviors indicate that teachers play an instrumental role in nurturing critical thinking skills among students. These skills are essential for promoting deeper understanding, independent inquiry, and effective problem-solving abilities.

On the other hand, the indicator “Facilitates problem-solving discussions” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.33. This means that some teachers are not confident in guiding discussions or encouraging collaborative solutions, they may feel less inclined to take on this role, leading to lower ratings on this indicator. The findings agreed with the study of Caong and Israel (2023) which found that leadership style in terms of critical

thinking is essential among leaders. However, Lusung et al. (2023) found that leadership styles in terms of critical thinking does not reflect leadership styles among teachers.

Findings revealed that the indicator “Promotes open communication” got the highest weighted mean of 3.11. This indicates that leaders promote open communication creates an atmosphere of trust and transparency. They perceived that when employees feel that their ideas and concerns are valued and heard, they are more likely to contribute innovative solutions without fear of judgment or reprisal.

It was found that the indicator “Facilitates problem-solving discussions” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.77. This means that some leaders adhere to traditional hierarchical structures and command-and-control leadership styles, which prioritize directive problem-solving over critical thinking and collaboration. The findings agreed with the study by Cimene et al. (2022) which found that school leaders who promote open communication and encourage questioning and reflection contribute to the development of critical thinking skills among staff. Similarly, Padillo et al. (2020) highlighted the importance of challenging assumptions and fostering a culture of inquiry in promoting critical thinking in educational organizations.

The indicator “Fosters a culture where problem-solving is not just reactive but proactive” got the highest weighted mean of 3.98. This means that teachers have received strong training on proactive problem-solving approaches, such as identifying potential issues before they escalate. This means that leaders demonstrate the value of proactive problem-solving, encouraging teams to embrace this approach. This consistent application of proactive problem-solving techniques results in teachers’ feeling that this approach is a cultural norm, thereby leading to high ratings. On the other hand, the indicator “Fosters a collaborative problem-solving environment” got the lowest weighted mean of 3.10. This means that the school or institution have a culture that emphasizes individual achievement over teamwork.

Among school heads, the indicator “Exhibits agility in decision-making” got the highest weighted mean of 3.11. This means that the school head knows how important the decision-making is, especially in the school settings. This also implies that school heads give importance in every situation that needs to be given solution. On the other hand, the indicator “Explores unconventional solutions encouraging creativity and adaptability” which got the lowest weighted mean of 2.73. This implies that school heads try to find ways by soliciting ideas from the group. This also means that the school heads often do not accept some ideas from others due to their experiences in the school. The findings of the study agreed with Aquino et al. (2021) and Daing and Mustapha (2022) which found that teachers foster collaboration in problem-solving which enhances their leadership styles and thereby influences students. The findings also agreed with the study of Cimene et al. (2022) which found that school leaders who promote a proactive problem-solving culture contribute to improved organizational performance and student outcomes.

The results indicated a favorable perception of teachers' communication skills, particularly in the domain of listening. The indicator “Exhibits empathy in their listening

skills” got the highest weighted mean of 3.22. This means that teachers demonstrate genuine interest to others, exhibit empathy, clarify and summarize information accurately, recognize non-verbal cues, and provide constructive feedback.

On the other hand, the indicator “Attuned to non-verbal cues and recognizes meanings conveyed” and the indicator “Demonstrates genuine interest for others” got the lowest weighted mean of 3.13. This means that teachers often have high workloads and multiple responsibilities, which limits their capacity to pay close attention to non-verbal cues.

Findings revealed that school heads “Exhibits empathy in their listening skills” which got 3.27 highest weighted mean. This means that employees feel psychologically safe when they believe their leaders genuinely care about their well-being and are receptive to their input. This also means that leaders demonstrate empathy in their listening skills practice active listening, focusing on understanding the speaker's emotions and underlying messages.

On the other hand, “Demonstrates genuine interest for others” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.89. This indicates that leaders engage in superficial or transactional interactions with their team members, focusing solely on task-related discussions rather than building genuine relationships. Findings of this study are supported by Padillo (2020) which found that empathy to others help improve listening skills. However, Caong and Israel (2023) found lower significance in the listening skills among teachers which contradicts the findings of this study. Moreover, the findings of this study agreed with the study by Padillo et al. (2020) which found that school leaders who demonstrate empathy and active listening skills contribute to improved staff morale and job satisfaction. Moreover, Caong and Israel (2023) found that leadership’s listening skills improves teachers’ performances.

Teachers are perceived to express themselves clearly and concisely got the highest weighted mean of 3.22. This indicates that clear and concise communication is critical for effective teaching. On the other hand, the indicator “Adapts communication styles to suit audience” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.43. This indicates that teachers often have heavy workloads and numerous responsibilities, leaving them with limited time to focus on adapting their communication styles. The findings of the study are supported by the study of Silva (2021) which found that listening skills helps improve teacher performance as they gain confidence in capturing student’s attention. Similarly, Zabala (2021) agreed with the findings revealed that charismatic and command and control showed of great significance in the speaking skills among teachers.

The data revealed that school heads “Adapts communication styles to suit audience” which got the highest weighted mean of 3.23. This means that school heads understand the needs of the audience and helps the audience perceive the communication as directly applicable to their roles and responsibilities. It also revealed that “Captures attention and facilitates better retention of information” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.94. This indicates that some leaders rely solely on verbal

communication without incorporating visual aids or multimedia elements to enhance engagement and aid in information retention.

The findings of the study are supported by the study of Silva (2021) which found that school leaders who effectively adapt their communication styles to suit diverse audiences contribute to improved stakeholder engagement and organizational outcomes. Moreover, the findings of Zabala (2021) also found that effective leadership styles influence the teachers through speaking skills promoting clear and concise information.

The highest grade found was Grade 12 while the lowest grade was the Grade 9. The slight increase in average grades as student progress to higher grade levels, with Grade 12 having the highest average, indicates a trend of improved academic performance as students advance through their academic journey. Factors such as increased maturity, familiarity with the curriculum, and specialized instruction in higher grades may contribute to this pattern. However, the Grade 9 which got the lowest grades implies that they have not fully advanced in their academic performance as the subjects and content taught are different across varying grade levels. The findings agreed with the study of Caong and Israel (2023) which found that leadership styles and teacher work motivation affects student's academic performances. On the contrary, Silva (2021) refuted the findings on significant relationship on leadership skills and the academic performance of students.

Further, the lack of significant relationship does not mean that the aforementioned leadership skills are irrelevant to academic performance; rather that there may be other relevant factors that may be important to leadership skills of the teachers. Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the leadership skills and learners' academic performance will not be rejected. The findings imply that while there is some influence of leadership skills, particularly problem-solving, on learners' academic performance, this influence is not statistically significant for leading innovation and critical thinking. This suggests that other factors beyond leadership skills play a more significant role in determining academic performance. The study by Daing and Mustapha (2022) supported the findings which found no significant positive relationship between transformational leadership practices and student achievement. Also, Aquino et al. (2021) failed to prove the significant relationship between the leadership skills and learners' academic performance.

Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the communication skills and learners' academic performance will not be rejected. Likewise, the results also indicates that there might be other skills aside from communication skills that might be relevant and crucial in determining the success in academics of the learners. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the communication skills and learners' academic performance will not be rejected. The findings imply that while there might be some influence of leadership skills, particularly Problem-Solving, on learners' academic performance, this influence is not statistically significant for Leading Innovation and Critical Thinking. This suggests that other factors beyond leadership skills may play a more significant role in determining academic

performance. The results agreed with Lusung et al. (2023) which revealed that there is no significant relationship between the leadership skills and learners' academic performance.

Findings revealed that the indicator "Survey results or feedback sessions where teachers highlight the need for more training, workshops, or resources to enhance their skills" got the highest weighted mean of 2.95. Teachers may feel that the existing professional development opportunities are inadequate in both quantity and quality. This could mean there are not enough workshops, training sessions, or resources available to help them develop the necessary skills in organizational leadership and communication.

It also revealed that the indicator "Feedback or survey responses indicating a desire for more collaborative decision-making forums or mechanisms" got the lowest weighted mean of 2.52 among the challenges encountered by teachers and learners in the organizational leadership and communication skills of the school heads and teachers. The low weighted mean indicates that the existing forums or mechanisms for collaborative decision-making are already considered sufficient by teachers and learners. This suggests that, compared to other issues, there were already effective processes in place for collaboration and shared decision-making.

The findings are contrary to the study of Aquino et al. (2021) which found that only those less experienced teachers and school heads experiences challenges in the organizational leadership and communication skills. On the other hand, the study of Daing and Mustapha (2022) found that teachers themselves were not confident in their ability to carry out their responsibilities in terms of student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management which posed challenges to them.

The objective of training workshop is to enhance the leadership and communication skills of teachers, empowering them to create a positive, collaborative classroom and school environment by leading with influence, fostering trust, and supporting a culture of proactive engagement. That is why this three-day training workshop is imperative to address the needs of the teachers as to enhance their leadership and communication skills. This training workshop is more than a response to a study's findings; it is a strategic initiative aimed at empowering teachers to become transformative leaders.

This workshop directly addresses the identified need for skill enhancement, providing teachers with the resources and support they require to thrive in their evolving roles. Through targeted training in leadership and communication, teachers will be better prepared to create positive, inclusive learning environments and contribute meaningfully to the school's mission. The long-term impact of this workshop is expected to resonate throughout the school community, as teachers apply their enhanced skills to inspire students, collaborate with peers, and build a school culture that values growth, respect, and continuous learning.

Conclusions

The conclusions drawn from the study's findings are as follows:

1. The findings reveal that teachers and school heads demonstrate strong leadership skills, particularly in fostering innovation, critical thinking, and problem-solving. These competencies are essential in adapting to the evolving educational landscape and addressing challenges effectively. Such skills play a crucial role in improving overall school performance, promoting a culture of innovation, and ensuring the holistic development of learners.

2. The findings indicate that teachers and school heads possess a high level of communication skills, including speaking and writing abilities. These competencies are critical in fostering effective communication within the school community, enhancing collaboration among stakeholders, and ensuring the clear and accurate conveyance of ideas and information. Such skills contribute significantly to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of teaching and school leadership.

3. Organizational leadership and communication skills significantly contribute to the improved academic performance of learners during the school year 2022-2023. The findings underscore the role of effective leadership and communication practices among teachers and school heads in creating a supportive learning environment, fostering collaboration, and enhancing instructional delivery. These elements have positively influenced learners' academic achievements, reflecting the pivotal role of leadership and communication in educational success.

4. The study found no significant relationship between leadership skills and learners' academic performance. While leadership skills are essential for effective school management and fostering a positive learning environment, the findings indicate that they do not directly influence learners' academic achievements.

5. The study found no significant relationship between communication skills and learners' academic performance. While communication skills are essential for effective interaction, collaboration, and leadership in educational settings, the findings suggest that they do not directly influence academic achievement.

6. The challenges related to a lack of training and resources hinder the effective application of organizational leadership and communication skills in enhancing learners' achievement. These challenges highlight the need for continuous professional development and adequate resource allocation to empower educators and school leaders in fulfilling their roles effectively.

7. Teachers face challenges requiring targeted professional development to enhance their organizational leadership and communication skills. To address these needs, a three-day training workshop was recommended. This initiative aims to equip educators with practical strategies and tools to overcome challenges, improve their skills,

and contribute more effectively to learners' achievement. The proposed workshop underscores the importance of continuous capacity building in ensuring educational success.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Teacher training programs may incorporate leadership skills development to prepare educators for leadership roles and equip them with the necessary skills to address complex challenges effectively.

2. Schools may continue to support and encourage teachers and school heads to maintain their high communication standards through ongoing training, workshops, and communication-focused professional development programs.

3. Encourage school heads and teachers to adopt collaborative leadership styles that actively involve all stakeholders, fostering a culture of shared responsibility and improved learning outcomes.

4. While leadership skills may not directly affect academic performance, school heads and teachers may focus on utilizing their leadership abilities to create supportive environments that enhance teaching and learning processes.

5. While communication skills may not directly impact academic performance, educators and school heads may use these skills to foster a collaborative and supportive school culture that indirectly supports learning.

6. Schools may offer regular training sessions focusing on advanced leadership and communication skills to equip teachers and school heads with strategies to overcome challenges and enhance their effectiveness.

7. Design the workshop modules to address specific skill gaps, such as advanced communication techniques, collaborative leadership strategies, and resource management, ensuring relevance to teachers' roles and responsibilities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher obtained informed consent from respondents by clearly outlining the purpose, procedures, and potential risks of the research. Also, the request for parental consent was given to the learners before the conduct of the survey. Respondents were assured that their identities and responses were kept private throughout and after the study and especially their academic achievement records. The use of anonymous codes or pseudonyms helped to further anonymize respondent data, reducing the risk of unintentional disclosure. To prevent unauthorized access, the researcher used secure

data storage and management practices such as password protection and encryption. Access to confidential information were restricted which will contribute to a controlled environment.

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